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Homeobox activation in childhood brain cancer.

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We measured total transcription in a collection of childhood brain tumors, including ATRT, pilocytic astrocytoma, glioblastoma, medulloblastoma, adamantinomatous craniopharyngioma, ependymoma, ependymoma (supratentorial ZFTA-RELA fusion), ganglioma, and diffuse midline glioma. We report here activation of a network of homeobox transcription factors as a common requisite transcriptional component of tumors from children with brain cancer. The network included factors HoxA10 and HoxA11, Lhx1 and Lhx4, Hmgb3, Hmgxb4, Sox4 and Sox11, OTX2, FoxA1 and FoxA2, FoxJ3, Six3 and ONECUT2.